

STRATEGIC APPLICATION OF SUN TZU'S, ART OF WAR IN EDUCATIONAL DIAGNOSTICS AND THERAPY

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Introduction

Although the historicity of Sun Tzu (b.544BC-d.496BC), also known as Sunzi, by pinyin transliteration, is uncertain, he is still being revered in Chinese and East Asian culture as a legendary historical and military figure. A Chinese military strategist, writer and philosopher, Sun Tzu's birth name was Sun Wu and he was also known as Changqing outside his family. The name by which he is known as Sun Tzu in literature today is an honorific title which means Master Sun.

Sun Tzu lived during the Eastern Zhou era of ancient China.

Traditionally, Sun Tzu has been credited as the author of the 13-chapter, "*The Art of War*," (see Tzu, 5th century BC/2013) – an influential work of military strategies that has not only impacted on the East Asian philosophy and military thinking but also the West, too. For instance, the Viet Minh commanders Vo Nguyen Giap and Ho Chi Min applied Sun Tzu's military strategies in the Vietnam War. In another example, the American generals Norman Schwarzkopf and Colin Powell

A pencil drawing of Sun Tzu

had also employed the principles from Sun Tzu's treatise during the Gulf War against the Iraqi army.

"*The Art of War*," (TAW for short) and the other works of Sun Tzu give more emphasis on alternatives to battle, e.g., "stratagem, delay tactics, establishing and sustaining alliances, the use of spies and different forms of deceit, the art of temporary submissiveness to more powerful foes, and other alternatives to war itself," (Carman, Harding, & Carmen, 2013, p.41). However, the principles from Sun Tzu's work can also be applied in conducting diplomatic, business and trade negotiations between companies and countries. Moreover, the principles from Sun Tzu's TAW have been used in many other areas including in our daily lives as well as sports, cyber-gaming, medicine, education ... and the list can go on.

In this short article, we want to share with our readers – professionals in the fields of counseling and other forms of therapies – three selected principles from Sun Tzu's TAW that we have used and applied in educational diagnostics and therapy (EDT) (Chia, 2010; Chia, Lim, & Lee, 2017).

A Brief Introduction to Educational Diagnostics and Therapy

There are two specialized fields closely related to special education: (1) Educational Diagnostics; and (2) Educational Therapy. Putting the two fields of specialization together, we shall call it Educational Diagnostics & Therapy (or EDT for short). There is a difference between the two fields.

On the one hand, the "educational diagnostics dives deeper into the areas of assessment and educational programming," (University of the Southeast, 2019, para.1). It covers the use of formal and informal assessments to make decisions regarding determining the presence of learning and/or behavioral disabilities/disorders, placement options, and needed services.

On the other hand, the educational therapy, as defined by the Association of Educational Therapists (2017), "combines educational and therapeutic approaches for evaluation, remediation, case management, and communication/advocacy on behalf of children, adolescents and adults with learning disabilities or learning problems," (para.1). Educational diagnosticians and therapists work closely with families of children and/or adults with disabilities/disorders to ensure that every individual with special needs is provided an individualized and appropriate education plan while enrolled in public schools and higher institutes of education.

Application of Sun Tzu's, "*The Art of War*" Principles in EDT

There are three phases of fit in the EDT framework: The first phase is known as Relevance of EDT; the next phase is the Appropriateness of EDT; and the last phase is Effectiveness of EDT. These three phases of fit constitute the EDT protocol for two key tasks: (1) To screen or administer diagnostic assessment of a 'learning and/or behavioral disability/disorder' (known as 'problematic condition' in this article) for the purpose of evaluating assessment data and establishing a client's profile based on the findings gathered from the assessment; and (2) To design a treatment plan (i.e., there are three types: intervention, rehabilitation, and/or management) based on the findings of the screening or assessment. According to the Center for Substance Abuse Treatment (2009), there is a key difference between screening and assessment: the former refers to a process for

evaluating the possible presence of a particular problematic condition, while the latter refers a process for defining the nature of that problematic condition, determining a diagnosis and developing specific treatment recommendations for addressing the problem or diagnosis. Each of these three phases will be briefly described and accompanied with a selected principle from Sun Tzu's TAW.

Phase #1 Relevance of EDT: In the first phase of the EDT framework, a question to ask here is: "How relevant is our current knowledge and understanding about a problematic condition when we carry out the EDT protocol?" Underlying this question is Sun Tzu's principle of: "*#1 If you know the enemy and know yourself, you need not fear the result of a hundred battles. #2 If you know yourself but not the enemy, for every victory gained you will also suffer a defeat. #3 If you know neither the enemy nor yourself, you will succumb in every battle.*" (Tzu, 5th Century BC/2013; Chapter 3-Attack in Stratagem, Point 18, p.12). This TAW principle can be further divided into three underlining principles as follows (see Chia, 2010, for detail):

Principle #1 If you know about the problematic condition, and are also aware of how much you know about its variant and non-variant traits, you are in a better position to administer an appropriate diagnostic assessment and also prepare a favorable intervention program with no fear of failure. This has been termed as the principle of targeted EDT (Chia, 2010).

Principle #2 If you are ignorant of the problematic condition, but are aware of how much you know about its variant and non-variant traits, your chances of success or failure in administering an appropriate diagnostic assessment and also preparing a favorable intervention program are equal. This has been termed as the principle of symptomatic approach in EDT (Chia, 2010).

Principle #3 If you are ignorant both of the problematic condition and are also unaware of its variant and non-variant traits, you are sure to fail in administering an appropriate diagnostic assessment or offering a favorable intervention. This is what Chia (2010) has termed it as the principle of sure chaotic approach in EDT, "At all cost, this last principle should warn anyone who is not well informed or trained to help individuals with problematic conditions to administer any diagnostic assessment or offer wrong advice or intervention that can become detrimental to these individuals" (Chia, 2010, p.124).

In other words, every diagnostician and therapist must always be well informed and updated on the latest or current developments in their respective fields of specialization if they are going to tackle challenging traits arising from varied problematic conditions. New discoveries in science, especially in medicine, are made every day and new inventions in engineering and technology are also developed all the times. Hence, we must keep ourselves abreast of all these new developments. There is no time for us to rest on our laurels or soon we will find ourselves lagging behind others in our respective professional fields of specialization.

Phase #2 Appropriateness of EDT: In the second phase of EDT framework, a question to ask here is: "How appropriate is the assessment done to obtain the diagnosis and to plan for the right treatment for a problematic condition when we carry out the EDT protocol?" Underlying this question is Sun Tzu's principle of, "*Thus we may know that there are five essentials for victory: #1 He will win who knows when to fight and when not to fight; and #2 He will win who knows how to handle both superior and inferior forces,*" (Tzu, 5th Century BC/2013; Chapter 3-Attack in

Stratagem, Point 187, p.11). First, we need to know what the five essentials are. According to Sun Tzu (5th Century BC/2013), they are, "(1) The Moral Law; (2) Tian (literally, it means Heaven); (3) Di (literally, it means Earth); (4) The Commander; and (5) Method and Discipline," (Chapter 1-Laying Plans, Point 4, p.1). When adapted to the EDT, these five essentials refer to (E1) The Code of Professional Practice; (E2) Specialized Content Knowledge required for the job; (E3) Practical Skills and Experience accumulated over the years of professional practice; (E4) The Educational Diagnostician or Therapist; and (E5) Professional Technique and Discipline that have been acquired over time.

With the five essentials in place, this TAW principle can be further divided into two underlining principles as follows:

Principle #1 An educational diagnostician or therapist must know when to assess (i.e., appraise or evaluate), diagnose (i.e., to identify the cause or problematic condition) and intervene (i.e., to treat) in order to ensure that the diagnostic assessment and/or follow-up intervention will be correctly and properly carried out. It is also equally important to know when not to assess, diagnose and/or intervene, too. The goal is to ensure the client's well-being is properly taken care of and be given the first priority among all things. For instance, Chia, Lim and Lee (2017) have illustrated using a child with autism who is given to frequent bouts of emotional outburst. It is essential for a professional to differentiate between temper tantrum and meltdown. It is proper to intervene when it is a temper tantrum but not when it is a meltdown, which must run its full course. From this first principle, the diagnostician or therapist (E4) has his/her code of professional practice (E1) to follow or adhere to, with the specialized content knowledge (E2) to know the difference between temper tantrum and meltdown though both are emotional outbursts, and the experience (E3) to know how to manage the challenging behavior using the appropriate technique and discipline already acquired previously (E5).

Principle #2 In order to assess, diagnose and intervene, a diagnostician or therapist must know when, what and how to use the available diagnostic test tools (e.g., for screening or assessment; standardized or non-standardized; core or supplementary) and the intervention strategies to study, understand and address a serious problematic condition. These diagnostic test tools and intervention strategies are like the weapons for the diagnostician or therapist to use in fighting the ravaging learning and/or behavioral disability/disorder (problematic condition). Among the test tools and intervention strategies, there are those which are superior and there are those which are inferior. An inferior test tool or intervention strategy does not mean it is not useful or ineffective; it is best used with a problematic condition that is at its initial onset and not too serious. In the same way, cancer is not treated the same way for all cases but has to depend on its four different stages of severity. A patient having the first stage cancer is not going to receive the same treatment as another patient with the third stage cancer,

"It was a great weekend! Let me reiterate my pride in this organization... Thank you for embracing an evolving business and carrying us into the future. I also look forward to a return to physical EMBRACING some day... but in the meantime, a nasty virus can't stop a flexible force! Thank you! Thank you! Thank you!"

-Karen Hand, Chicago, IL

whose treatment has become more intensive. A professional, therefore, should know how to choose the appropriate tools for the diagnostic assessment and/or right strategies for treatment of the problematic condition. From this second principle, the same five essentials are applied: the diagnostician or therapist (E4) following his/her code of professional practice (E1), applying the specialized content knowledge (E2) and accumulated experience (E3) to use the appropriate diagnostic test tools and/or intervention strategies (E5) to manage the problematic condition.

In other words, every diagnostician and therapist must know exactly when, what and how to assess and diagnose a problematic condition and to intervene the condition with an appropriate intervention plan. To do it successfully requires the professional to know exactly what or which diagnostic test tools are most appropriate to administer, and what or which intervention strategies to be used in treatment.

Phase #3 Effectiveness of EDT: In this third and final phase, a question to ask here is: "How effective is the educational diagnostics and therapy in screening/assessing and treating the problematic condition?" Underlying this question is Sun Tzu's principle of "a strategy without tactics is a slow progress to victory; tactics without a strategy is making noise before defeat." (Tzu, 5th Century BC; translated by Giles, 2005). This TAW principle is adapted in the context of EDT to mean that, on one hand, administering a diagnostic assessment without a clearly defined assessment protocol to follow and/or carrying out an intervention approach without a clearly designed plan of action will result in a slow progress to improvement in remedying or managing the problematic condition. On the other hand, a clearly defined assessment protocol without properly administering a diagnostic assessment or carrying out a plan of action without a clearly defined intervention approach is humbugging before failure.

In other words, every diagnostician and therapist must be fully aware that the effectiveness of EDT depends on him/her being very familiar with the assessment protocol to ensure a proper administration of diagnostic assessment and/or being thorough in designing a plan of action to ensure that an intervention approach is correctly carried out.

*"Just a short note to say **THANK YOU** for allowing me to contribute to your **SUCCESSFUL 2020** conference. Your team, who assisted me with my preparation and presentation were true professionals."*

-Gary Lalonde, Port St Lucie, FL

Conclusion

As we come to the concluding part of this short article, we want to sum up by quoting from Sun Tzu, "He who knows these things, and in fighting puts his knowledge into practice, will win his battles. He who knows them not, nor practices them, will surely be defeated." (Tzu, 5th century BC/2-13; Chapter 10-Terrain, Point 22, p.48).

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But how do I offer the vibration of wellness when I am sick? And we say, by remembering when you were well, by imagining that you are well, by pretending that you are well, by de-emphasizing the fact that you are sick and re-emphasizing the feeling of wellness.

Abraham